

101112135 - IDERHA

Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory
and HTA Acceptance

WP5 Ethical and legal framework

D5.7 Appraisal of obstacles to data use and reuse
case

Lead contributor	30 - HYG
Other contributors	5 - The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD) 1 - Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. (FHI) 2 – JJM 3 - LYG

Data	Description
Due date	30-11-2025
Delivery date	25-11-2025
Delivery type	R
Dissemination level	PU

Document History

Version	Date	Description
v0.20	31-Oct-2025	This draft after Utrecht SCOM in October 2025
v0.50	10-Nov-2025	Final draft for approval after WP5 feedback
v0.60	25/11/2025	Final draft for IHI submission after MB feedback

Executive Summary

This deliverable, D5.7, is a report on the legal and regulatory requirements affecting wider data-sharing for reuse of IDERHA data sources including an assessment of their limiting effects. The issues encountered ('obstacles') are distinct from the 'policy gaps' considered by WP6 in their considerations and deliverables. For clarity, WP5 focuses on legal and regulatory obstacles encountered by IDERHA, while WP6 addresses external policy gaps beyond the project's control.

Glossary

Term	Definition
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence or Machine Learning algorithms or processing generally
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CT	Clinical Trial
DC	Dynamic Consent
DGA	Data Governance Act
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EMR	Electronic Medical Record (usually held within a clinic or institution)
EHR	Electronic Health Record (possibly shared across institutions over time)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICF	Informed Consent Form
IRB	Institutional Review Board (=REC)
PI	Principal Investigator (of a research study or clinical trial)
PIL	Patient Information Leaflet
REC	Research Ethics Committee (=IRB)
RWD	Real World Data
SDE	Secure Data Environment (also SPE or TRE)
SPE	Secure Processing Environment (also SDE or TRE)
TRE	Trusted Research Environment (also SDE or SPE)

Introduction

This deliverable was developed as part of Task 5.3:

Task 5.3. (HYG with I~HD, EPF, LYG, FHI, LBI-DHP, ECPC, Roche)

Assess the legal, regulatory and ethical obstacles to wide scale health data reuse and provide recommendations to stakeholders and EHDS

Figure 1- Development of Deliverables D5.7 and D5.10

The diagram illustrates the interaction between the development of this deliverable, D5.7, and that of D5.10.

Deliverable Description:	<i>Report on the <u>legal and regulatory requirements</u> affecting wider data-sharing for reuse of IDERHA data sources including an assessment of their limiting effects.</i>
--------------------------	--

There were no ‘ethical’ obstacles encountered, though there were plenty of ‘ethical issues’ to be considered, which did not prove to be ‘obstacles’ for the IDERHA project.

The possible overlap between ‘obstacles’ (WP5) and ‘policy gaps’ (WP6) was resolved at the Berlin SCOM in April 2024:

Obstacle	A problem encountered by IDERHA which it may have been able to resolve within project constraints, or may have had to compromise objectives because of resource constraints
Policy Gap	A problem which might have been encountered by IDERHA or similar projects, which could only be resolved by external parties (hence a ‘policy gap’)

Methods

The T5.3 team went through a number of exercises to establish their final list of 'obstacles':

- The team drew up a list of possible 'obstacles' based on past experience and mapped these out – from this a conceptual structure for possible obstacles was developed. This was not limited to merely 'legal and 'regulatory' obstacles as issues might initially be considered under other headings but have a 'root cause' which would be under the 'legal' or 'regulatory' headings.
- A survey of the wider IDERHA consortium was undertaken to solicit a more complete list of obstacles using the proposed 'obstacle' categories, but still based mainly on experience prior to IDERHA, as the project had not yet been active for long.
- When results were presented at the Berlin SCOM in 2024 and the possible overlap with WP6 debated, it became clear that, while useful in conceptual terms, much of the work undertaken would need to be re-framed (so the work undertaken to this point is not presented here).
- A revised list of 10 possible 'obstacles' developed by the T5.3 team was later presented at the Vienna SCOM meeting in November 2024, mainly to get feedback on how relevant these were to the wider project members and to identify possible obstacles that the T5.3 team had missed or were not aware of.
- Based on the feedback from the Vienna SCOM and after 'root cause analysis' to identify those underlying aspects that generated the problem encountered, a revised list of 8 obstacles was presented to the wider project team for them to comment on the level of 'impact' of these 8 obstacles on the project, assessing their limiting effects.

This final list of legal and regulatory obstacles with the weightings received are the basis of this report.

Results

Initial conceptual structure

The range of issues to be considered were put under these headings:

- **Ethical Issues** – issues of what is 'right' to do¹
- **Legal Issues** – both fundamental and because of different jurisdictions
- **Regulatory Issues** – usually about enacting the legal and ethical requirements
- **Cultural Issues** – across and within different Member States
- **Structural Issues** – relating to the organization of a local health economy
- **Communication Issues** – between relevant parties and to the public at large
- **Technology Issues** – ability to implement systems requirements as well as the ever-changing technology landscape
- **Scientific/Methodological Issues** – aspects about appropriate analysis of the data, including data quality for research and regulatory purposes

¹ Administrative issues to do with ethics committees would be considered 'Regulatory' issues

Obstacles as presented in Vienna (Nov. 2024)

	Title	Notes
1.	The laws and regulations to health data sharing are not harmonised.	National and regional authorities can and have imposed rules which preserve a heterogeneous environment, despite the attempt of establishing a pan- EU data market. This is linked to healthcare being a member state responsibility and not an EC mandate. International (EU) law does not overrule national law, because of the explicit ability for MS to impose additional rules, therefore a pan-EU data market where data can flow freely (the EU's original ambition) is not likely to emerge soon.
2.	The number of applicable laws and regulations in the EU has grown substantially (GDPR, DGA, DA, AI, MPD, IVDR, MDR1, ..), which make data sharing a humongous regulatory task.	The cost and risks involved, increase hurdles to enter the data mart and impose a burden on existing parties who use or provide data in the healthcare system. The complexity of applicable laws and regulations is beyond any one individual's competences and requires an interaction of experts across the whole scope of the intended processing (geographically, or purposes, legal domains, data and health sciences)
3.	There is ambiguity in interpreting applicable laws and regulations (by each supervisory authorities, profession/trade bodies, lawyers, DPOs).	Case law is lacking or emerging, which leads to still prevailing conservatism, notably if (as usual) the data holder has no benefit from sharing their data but potential compliance exposure.
4.	Procedures and documentation necessary for further processing are enormous	e.g. List of processing activities, data protection impact assessment, consent/opt-out, agreements with processors, breach procedures, technical operating model (incl. security controls), privacy policy, process for withdrawals, disclosures, which implies cost, effort and time to comply.
5.	There are persisting rules, intentional or not, which preserve privileges, historical complications, local institutional roles (e.g. EAB, jurisdiction) or service precedence, processing, or interest.	Example: Regional rules to include local PIs, local EAB and local interest as a requirement to any data sharing (Spain) Example: Broad consent in Germany requires one specific local form and wording to be used for the consent to be valid.
6.	Ill-designed burden of proof and liability regime	For example, having to prove compliance to all applicable rules and documentation requirements, as opposed to not cause any harm (or violation of personal rights) with the party suffering damage to prove the case. This contradicts well known concepts such as product liability rules and leads to a pressure for overcompliance for data sharing parties. However, this got better in the more recent laws (e.g. AI act which allows for class action). This can be evidenced in conceptual differences in GDPR (fines by a supervisory authority) vs AI Act (burden of proof with the party suffering harm, but with instruments, e.g. class action) to overcome imbalances of knowledge and power.

	Title	Notes
7.	Accepted data quality standards not implemented yet.	There are no generally accepted or legally required attestations or attributes to data which are shared, neither voluntary nor mandatory, so that data users know on what they can rely. Ambiguity around accuracy, correctness, authenticity, integrity persists, induce error and uncertainty in and downstream processing of such data. This is further aggravated by lacking quality standards in maintaining the original master records in the first place.
8.	Data exchange standards and common ontologies are not implemented.	While it is commonly recognised that common formats of data storage and transfer would help the sharing, largely, these do exist only partially or are not implemented, certainly not at scale. Data is stored in different formats, schemas, and with different meanings (ontologies, semantics) and are not standardised, nor easily translated or transferred among these databases. This leads to laborious curation, labelling, translation and transfer processes, which are again not standardised themselves, leading to growing interface complexity, effort, and time require to effect data transfers.
9.	There is ambiguity on what legal basis is best to be used for data sharing and what role opting-out or -in (consent) plays in which cases and what information and documentation is required for such sharing.	De-identified sharing for general interest R&D, legitimate interest by the Data User, or explicit opt-out/-in are typical alternatives with associated requirements each.
10.	It is not clear what assurance a data holder requires to authenticate a data user to be granted access to data.	This applies to citizen accessing their own data, as well as professionals, who seek to access R&D datasets. How sure must a data holder be before releasing data? Is a user account with a research or healthcare organisation good enough? Is a copy of a photo ID required or does a digital ID of a qualified trust service provider suffice to authenticate a patient, yet at what assurance level? Do patients have to prove possession of social security or insurance numbers or patient IDs?

SCOM participants were asked (using Mentimeter app) for their appraisal of each of the obstacles on a scale of 1-5 (Do you “strongly agree”, “agree”, “neutral”, “disagree”, or “strongly disagree”?). Participants were also asked for any additional ‘obstacles’ they thought should be included.

Figure 2- Assessment of IDERHA Obstacles to data sharing in November 2024 (19 months into the project)

Obstacles as presented in Utrecht (Oct. 2025)

Based on the feedback from Vienna and root cause analysis carving out the underlying factor which requires to be addressed, the resulting 8 risk categories were presented to the eSCOM for validation and to assess their implication on sharing.

Cat	Seq	Obstacle	Notes
Ethical			[No immediate Ethical obstacles]
Legal	L1	Multiple applicable laws	e.g. GDPR, AI Act, DGA, MDR, ...
	L2	Legal uncertainties or ambiguities	e.g. Pseudo-/anonymous data
	L3	Contractual aspects	JCA, CA, DPIA, DMP, DSAs ...
Regulatory	R1	Gaining 'approvals'	Different bodies with different responsibilities in different regions
	R2	Lack of regulatory guidance	Often late and incomplete
	R3	Excess of interpretive guidance	Inconsistent & not authoritative
	R4	Lack of 'accepted practice'	e.g. data-only projects, double-pseudonymisation, federated or distributed processing
	R5	Excessive procedures & documentation	JCA, CA, DPIA, DMP, ...

SCOM participants were asked to rank the 'impact' of each obstacle from their perspective (whether from a personal, Task team, WP, or whole project view) by writing down their assessment with a brief explanation to add context. The rating approach was:

- **No impact** – if there were no impact² then it was not necessary to complete a Post-It entry
- **Minor** – the issue may have created some delay or required some additional resource, which was absorbed within existing budgets
- **Major** - the issue created significant delay or required additional resources, which affected budgets and may have required that some activities were dropped or not undertaken
- **Blocker** – the issue prevented the delivery of certain products (not necessarily deliverables) or delayed milestones

² Note that other partners or WPs may have experienced some impact, unknown to the participant

The results of the impact ranking exercise are shown below:

Obs Ref	Blocker	Major	Minor	None	Total	Weighted	Ranking
L1		5	6	2	13	16	80%
L2	1	3	6	1	11	16	80%
L3		9	6		15	24	120%
R1	1	8	6	1	16	26	130%
R2		5	7	1	13	17	85%
R3		4	5		9	13	65%
R4	1	2	6		9	14	70%
R5		5	8		13	18	90%
Total	3	41	50	5	99		

While three obstacles were ranked as a 'blocker', this was not a general consensus – in each case only one person thought of the obstacle as a 'blocker'.

Applying a logarithmic weighting (Minor=1, Major=2, and Blocker=4) to reflect the relative level of impact and dividing it by 20 (roughly the number of respondents) gave an overall ranking (last column). This is far from a scientific measure, but allowed a rough-and-ready separation between:

- **Notable** obstacles:
 - R1: gaining approvals
 - L3: Contractual aspects
- **Important** obstacles:
 - R5: Excessive documentation
 - R2: Lack of regulatory guidance
 - L1: Multiple applicable laws
 - L2: Legal uncertainties or ambiguities
- **Minor** obstacles:
 - R4: Lack of 'accepted practice'
 - R3: Excess of interpretive guidance

Discussion

We discuss the specific obstacles under their category headings of: Ethical, Legal, and Regulatory.

We consider the 'impact' ranking as a separate aspect at the end.

Note: that these obstacles and possible recommendations as to how best to handle them will be part of the deliverable, **D5.10 - Results and recommendations for wide data sharing and consent models applicable to the EHDS**, due later in the project. More detailed discussion of the obstacles and the possible approaches will be developed there.

Ethical

There are a number of ethical issues that need to be considered by the project (though not by T5.3 team in producing D5.7 or D5.10), such as patient privacy, transparency, etc. However, none of these materialised as ethical 'obstacles' *per se*.

As an example, possible issues over consent or anonymisation were addressed by the approach defined in the project proposal that a federated system (which only returned statistical results) would be used – at least for the 'research' use-case.

Any difficulties gaining ethical approvals we have put under the headings 'Regulatory' or 'Structure' as it was more a question of delays encountered through regulatory process rather than a difficulty resolving any 'ethical' issues as such.

Legal

#L1: Multiple applicable laws

At the EU level, there are a range of laws to be considered by IDERHA or similar projects, from GDPR, through AI Act to Medical Devices Regulation. The interplay of these is not always clear nor how to manage to comply with all of them together.

Separately there is the difficulty of processing healthcare data, because healthcare is a Member State (MS) competency, there are often pre-existing laws concerning the processing of healthcare data, which would only apply in a particular MS or perhaps only in a particular region.

However, these have not necessarily presented as 'obstacles' to all parties in IDERHA. Data Providers are generally familiar with complying with their 'local' legislation as well as GDPR, etc. The IDERHA approach of federated data processing has simplified matters as only aggregate results or model parameters considered to be non-personal data would be shared outside of a particular Data Provider.

This may also explain why this obstacle was ranked as only 'Important': for many participants, it was either not a big issue or dealt with by specialists at their own organisation.

Hygiaso, in providing the citizen-app, has to consider the legal position for the citizen's locality (or wherever the citizen may have been treated over time, which could be different again). However, the core approach here is that of 'consent' (indeed 'dynamic consent') so the citizen chooses what should happen – and this is normally an acceptable legal basis under most legislations – though how an organisation may need to prove compliance can vary.

#L2: Legal uncertainties or ambiguities

There are some possible ambiguities, where the correct interpretation of the law is unclear or unclear in some circumstances, e.g. 'pseudonymised data' is sometimes held to necessarily be 'personal data' but could clearly also be 'anonymous data' (based on Recital 26), though that too is contentious as it is not clear quite what criteria should apply for the 'reasonably likely' test for re-identification. September 2025, the CJEU (*EDPS v SRB C-413/23 P*) has overturned a prior General Court decision from 2023 that such pseudonymised data is personal data and requires an analysis of each case. Some of these ambiguities add to the conservatism of institutions when considering data-sharing initiatives (see S2 below).

There is an open question about handling privacy risks when disclosing aggregate data or statistics, which can lead to some interpretations that aggregate data may still be 'personal data'. Generally, by avoiding 'uniques' in tables or applying small cell-count controls (or similar statistical disclosure techniques) the privacy risks are more easily controlled.

However, as noted above, by using a federated approach to processing, IDERHA has avoided the necessity of resolving questions concerning 'pseudonymous' or 'anonymous' data. This suggests that working within the boundaries (rather than at the boundaries) may perhaps be the best way forward as a pragmatic solution – leaving these questions to be addressed elsewhere (as possible 'policy gaps' perhaps), though remaining conservatively within the scope of allowable practice avoiding the borderline cases narrows the scope of data sharing and may constitute an obstacle.

Other questions still remain: to what degree are consortium partners all 'joint controllers'³ – do they collectively determine the 'purpose' and the 'means' of each processing step? At present, each Data Provider will perform the processing within their own systems but only after careful consideration of each Data Access Request which they alone (or at least in compliance with whatever local 'approvals' have been granted) decide whether to process or not. The Data User submitting the request (and any associated query/algorithm) may be regarded as determining the 'means' (alone or jointly?), even if the 'purpose' is part of the collective IDERHA brief; but there is no agreement that the operation requested will actually be performed. Further, the results from the processing will be monitored and approved before being sent from the federated node. This aspect was perhaps recognised more under L3: Contractual aspects rather than as a legal uncertainty.

#L3: Contractual aspects

There has been considerable work within IDERHA over establishing the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the role of the Data Management Plan (DMP) in defining various consortium partners roles and responsibilities for various aspects including GDPR compliance. It is not clear whether this has created any delay in actually progressing other activities, including gaining access to data, with IDERHA.

There is some indication that by subsuming the DMP into the CA in its entirety that it has undermined the usefulness of the DMP as a technical document detailing what current thinking is in terms of the detailed infrastructure and associated processes.

That this was considered the second most notable obstacle suggests that some further work is needed by IHI and other parties as to how best to structure the overall contractual arrangements – perhaps by a more nuanced approach to handling the Data Management Plan rather than including it wholesale into the Consortium Agreement. There is no doubt that the approach required significant work, and some of this may have been unavoidable, but could perhaps have been broken down into more manageable stages to avoid delays elsewhere.

³ It is not clear if and when the consortium may act as 'joint controllers' for GDPR purposes regarding the processing of personal data in general and/or the specific case at hand.

Regulatory

#R1: Gaining 'approvals'

Depending on the MS and region(s) within which the Data Provider operates, then different 'approvals' may be required from a range of 'oversight' bodies. This can create a range of difficulties which delay or make more complicated the gaining of these approvals (even assuming that there are no mistakes within the original applicant documents which might require amendment and re-application):

- Different forms to be completed (in paper and/or electronically)
- Differing application processes with variable timings (e.g. some bodies only meet quarterly, others 'as necessary') so predicting when applications might be considered and approved is difficult
- Different (and possibly conflicting) documentation requirements – possibly including approvals from other bodies
- Different opinions on, say, interpretation of the law or other regulations as well as appropriate wording to inform patients and the public
- Different aspects or scope for approval (some RECs are also expected to check GDPR compliance, despite being an organisational obligation)
- Differing and possibly conflicting opinions from approval bodies for different data sources (some countries have 'multi-centre' RECs so that only one approval is needed (at least for 'ethics!')). As most oversight bodies are 'independent' it means they can also be inconsistent!
- Often no appeal process

All of these elements (and possibly more) mean that gaining approvals is a fraught business, even for the well-prepared.

Even with all necessary regulatory approvals, the actual Data Provider management may not choose to provide the data anyway, or internal priorities mean that data provision is delayed.

It is clear from the impact ranking that this is assessed to be a significant problem for any healthcare data-sharing project – not just IDERHA.

The following diagram gives some sense of the multiple approvals that may be needed for a single Data Provider:

Figure 3 - Gaining Approvals & consequential delays

There may be many more 'approval' steps and some stages may require iteration – and at any stage, the Data Provider (as an organisation) may decide not to proceed or to delay action.

There can also be no doubt that novel uses of healthcare data are always going to create concern amongst 'approval' bodies or individuals, whereas 'routine' or familiar uses may be more readily approved without extensive review.

#R2: Lack of regulatory guidance

This is particularly true for guidance about compliance with new laws, such as the AI Act, though this was in part anticipated as part of the IDERHA project brief – that the project should explore and hopefully influence the development of such guidance.

Even for better established law, e.g. GDPR, there have been years of delays in guidance emerging. The EDPB only released draft guidelines on 'pseudonymisation' in January 2025.

The EDPB guidance on the concepts of 'controller' and 'processor' (published in 2020) discusses the question of 'joint controllership'. This still leaves a lot of flexibility (or ambiguity) for the parties involved, as to interpreting the key points of 'purpose' and 'means'. This is further highlighted by the CJEU case of SRB vs EDPS where it was disputed who was 'controller' and who was 'processor' under a contract in terms of supporting Article 13/14 rights. So much guidance is left somewhat vague, partly as the regulators themselves do not wish to commit themselves to one particular interpretation or another (preferring to wait for a court case to settle the matter).

This was rated as an 'important' obstacle, but not a complete 'blocker', possibly because ways were found around some of the uncertainties. It might also be considered to encompass R4 - Lack of 'accepted practice', which is perhaps more of a suggested 'solution' which might be part of any useful regulatory guidance.

#R3: Excess of interpretive guidance

There is a lot of guidance produced by various bodies to 'help' organisations understand what they need to do – however, it is not always consistent (between the sources) and often creates further confusion by re-phrasing the actual legal clauses.

The classic example is the taking of 'pseudonymised data is personal data' out of context. Early summary text by the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) in the UK included the phrase 'pseudonymised data is personal data' – it is notable that now (2025) it uses the slightly more accurate phrase: 'Pseudonymised data is personal data in the hands of someone who holds the additional information', allowing for the possibility that the pseudonymised data (as per Article 4 definition) does not actually use pseudonyms or that the data in the hands of the recipient might be considered anonymous (as per EDPS vs SRB⁴ CJEU judgment).

This was the lowest ranked of the obstacles in terms of impact, perhaps as many of the SCOM participants would look to primary guidance (so R2) rather than secondary guidance (or perhaps their own DPOs), which is perhaps most likely to be read only by technical specialists, who may not find it at all helpful.

#R4: Lack of 'accepted practice'

It seems that every data-sharing project needs to be re-examined in detail in order to gain the necessary 'approvals'. GDPR places the responsibility for compliance firmly on the controller (or joint controllers), but it seems that in other regulatory aspects the opposite applies – the compliance must be proven in advance to a range of oversight bodies. Admittedly, some of these 'oversight bodies' are the internal mechanism whereby a large data provider assures itself that the proposed project for which they are wholly (or at least in part) controller will be compliant.

If there were accepted models of 'good practice' to which a project might comply, then 'approvals' could be more readily granted – or even simply be subject to a 'registration' process (for transparency and accountability) which would be much more efficient.

⁴ Single Resolution Board (SRB), the central resolution authority within the eurozone Banking Union

GDPR actually allows for this in terms of Article 40/41 'Codes of Conduct', but the level of administration to get a draft 'code of conduct' approved vastly exceeds the current 'approvals' process(es) not matter how convoluted.

A positive exemplar might be that in the UK under GafREC guidelines⁵ projects not using identified patient information ('confidential patient information') do not require REC approval as it is considered that any 'ethics' issues are handled by GDPR or other 'local' legislation (which, of course, may require its own 'approvals').

As noted above, this obstacle might be considered subsidiary to R2: *Lack of regulatory guidance*; equally, it may be hard to experience the 'lack' of something as an obstacle, so SCOM participants may not have experienced it as an obstacle *per se*.

#R5: Excessive procedures & documentation

This obstacle was originally raised in the sense of GDPR 'accountability' principle and the increasing pressure on organisations to be able to 'prove' compliance with data-related laws (e.g. AI Act) before undertaking any processing of data.

Some IDERHA deliverables which might be covered under this heading are:

- D5.1 DPIA Guidance Framework – for GDPR compliance
- D5.4 Operational blueprint for regulatory compliance in IDERHA AI developments
- D5.5 AI transparency, data quality and bias documentation framework, per implementation
- D5.8 General data sharing policy within IDERHA
- D5.11 Report of the regulatory compliance, ethical and governance status of the implemented AI components – for AI Act compliance

In addition, there are a number of required contractual documents or products:

- Grant Agreement
- Consortium Agreement – where Appendix 14 includes:
 - D4.1 - Data Management Plan 1.docx
 - D4.4 Data Management Plan (2).docx
- Joint Controller Agreement
- Advisory Agreement – for external Committee members
- Consent Form template (English – as well as various translations)

There is no doubt that some deliverables were delayed by the extended negotiations around the Consortium Agreement and the DMP, e.g. D5.1 DPIA Guidance Framework – by the time this was complete, most of the immediate Data Providers would probably already have produced their own in-house DPIA, based on their local requirements.

From the SCOM feedback, this was felt to have been an important 'obstacle' which had delayed progress, though perhaps with some overspill from L3: Contractual aspects, where a general sense of excessive documentation may have arisen.

⁵ [Governance arrangements for Research Ethics Committees](#) (GafREC) July 2021)

Conclusion

The term 'obstacle' suggests some barrier to progress that would not have been anticipated when planning a project. There are clearly other barriers, such as limited funding, possible lack of expertise or experienced resources, that can hinder any project as it progresses, but are simply part of managing any project.

The initial IDERHA-wide survey in January 2024 high-lighted aspects of the final list of 'obstacles' from collective experience in other projects, suggesting that perhaps some of these issues could have been anticipated – though possibly with no obvious solution or way of working which could be included in the proposal design. It is difficult when developing a forward-looking research proposal to get bogged down in the project management minutiae – and flagging lots of potential problems may not enhance the likelihood of gaining funding!

The most notable obstacle was R1: Gaining Approvals. There is a natural tendency to presume that because a consortium partner has agreed to participate in a proposal that there is nothing much to prevent data-sharing – or that the 'local' participants know what to do – which they may, but over-optimism centrally may not recognise the actual complexity of approvals and time required to get data to flow (see Figure 2 above).

The other notable obstacle was L3: Contractual aspects, where IDERHA took a novel approach to the role of the DMP and JCA. The phrase 'if it isn't in the DMP, then it doesn't happen' was used to make clear that the set of legal agreements needed required the DMP to be finalised in a particularly complete way. This may in turn have delayed consortium partners from applying for approvals as they could not be sure of the detailed processing (as specified in the DMP).

For previous projects (based on the IHI template), the DMP had focused mainly on the FAIR principles compliance and only dealt with data processing at a broad level. The DPIA framework would normally dwell more on the detail of the data processing steps and controller-processor aspects (as well as GDPR and other legal compliance questions) though again leaving fine technical detail to other documents generated by the more technical WPs. While a much more manageable approach, it did leave a lot of questions to be resolved later in the project and meant that consortium partners might not all have a clear perspective on all that was happening in data-processing terms (or at least not in a readily available set of documents).

Some mid-ground approach needs to be found, so that risks are properly managed, but also that the components of a project can progress without delay.

It is clear from the discussions above that there are a number of inter-plays between the 'obstacles' identified, so even if individually anticipated, their combined effect could not be easily anticipated.

The following diagram gives some sense of possible interactions (there may be others):

Figure 4 – Possible interactions between the Obstacles

Next Steps

The output of this Deliverable will go forward into the development of the Deliverable, D5.10 – *Results and recommendations for wide data sharing and consent models applicable to the EHDS*, where the notable or important obstacles can be explored in more depth and recommendations for IDERHA and future projects be developed.

Appendix: Full list of ‘obstacles’ after RCA

Cat	Seq	Obstacle	Notes
			[No immediate Ethical obstacles]
Legal	L1	Multiple applicable laws	e.g. GDPR, AI Act, DGA, MDR, ...
	L2	Legal uncertainties or ambiguities	e.g. Pseudo-/anonymous data
	L3	Contractual aspects	JCA, CA, DPIA, DMP, DSAs ...
Regulatory	R1	Gaining ‘approvals’	Different bodies with different responsibilities in different regions
	R2	Lack of regulatory guidance	Often late and incomplete
	R3	Excess of interpretive guidance	Inconsistent & not authoritative
	R4	Lack of ‘accepted practice’	e.g. data-only projects, double-pseudonymisation, federated or distributed processing
	R5	Excessive procedures & documentation	JCA, CA, DPIA, DMP, ...
Cultural	C1	Type of health economy	Affects how healthcare is delivered and so how data is collected and how it should be interpreted
	C2	Collective versus individual ethos varies between Member States	May make ‘approvals’ harder to gain in some places
Structural	S1	Healthcare is a Member State competency, which creates diverse requirements	So different rules have applied and not been ‘tidied up’ to allow for GDPR, etc.
	S2	Incentives & disincentives	Data Providers have all the risk but no gain
	S3	‘Tipping point’ issues	Need enough providers and users to make viable
Comms.	I1	Transparency and informing the public effectively	What do people want/need to know?; what do they know already?; coping with literacy levels
	I2	Having to manage in PILs and ICFs in multiple languages & countries	Multiple languages, contexts, approval bodies (who like to tweak PILs/ICFs)
Tech	T1	Overhead in transposing data into diverse exchange standards	Making data interoperable without impairing it
	T2	Unclear authentication needs	Practical mean of proving who a citizen or clinician is so we can share data between them.
Data	D1	Real-world data are diverse	Fact-of-life, but how best to analyse such data
	D2	Data Quality standards	Helping people understand & improve their data

Supporting explanations for the excluded categories of obstacles are as follows:

Cultural

#C1: Type of health economy

This can affect interpretation of data as it may affect the healthcare process: in a wholly 'private' health economy patients are likely to make different choices from those in a wholly state-funded 'universal' health economy; aspects of healthcare that are not covered by state or insurance provision may be deferred or not treated at all. Co-payments may also affect patient behaviour in terms of choice of treatment or whether to 'wait and see'.

#C2: Collective versus individual ethos varies between Member States

This may affect the level of trust in data-sharing for the benefit of all; some countries and patient populations seem to accept the idea of 'national' healthcare databases more readily than others. This may be reflected in the type of media coverage too, which in turn may alter levels of opt-out that might be experienced.

Structural

#S1: Healthcare is a Member State competency which creates diverse requirements

This affects the choice of health economy (see #C1 above) as well as prioritisation and how healthcare resources are deployed. 'Local' legislation can be a bit of an issue (see #L1 above) but scarcely an 'obstacle' in its own but with the diversity of approaches required with multiparty international sharing.

This is probably more of a 'structural difficulty' rather than an 'obstacle' to be overcome. It is the way things are!

#S2: Incentives & disincentives

There can be several aspects here:

- Initial funding for change – implementation would require redeployment of resources from other initiatives or direct care of patients
- Future benefit uncertain or accrues to other parties – the likely future benefits from data-sharing can be hard to quantify
- Risk aversion – the 'gate-keeper' problem: the person (or persons) making the decision may receive little credit for approving the data-sharing when it goes well, but very likely suffer reputational damage if they approve and it subsequently goes wrong or is held to be non-compliant – especially where they have all of the risks and none of the rewards
- Public vs commercial use – in state-funded or public insurance-based health economies, there can be considerable concern about private exploitation of data, both in terms of possible improper use or simply by private profit from public actions.
- Intellectual property – either informally, that someone has worked hard to gather the particular dataset, or that the cost of collecting the dataset needs to be defrayed in some way.

These can play out in many ways, but generally means that potential data providers have little reason to hasten to share their data, unless there is some more direct incentive to do so.

This has not necessarily been an 'obstacle' for IDERHA as consortium partners have funding to help establish the planned data-sharing, but may prove to be an obstacle in the future when seeking to gain wider acceptance.

#S3: 'Tipping point' issues

For data exchanges, such as IDERHA, to be sustainable, there need to be sufficient data providers (with useful/usable data) providing access to data as well as sufficient data users/consumers to justify having the infrastructure – as well as to pay for the service.

Again, this is not an immediate 'obstacle' for IDERHA but may become so in the future.

Communications

#1: Transparency and informing the public effectively

Again, probably more of a 'difficulty' than an obstacle. It is difficult to inform the public about IDERHA (or similar activities) when it is not usually a 'front of mind' concern for most citizens (though can easily become so through adverse publicity). Lack of understanding of either (or both) of the technologies deployed or the overall rationale/need for scientific research can mean that people will react to adverse publicity without fully understanding the consequences

#2: Having to manage PILs and ICFs in multiple languages & countries

Yet again, perhaps a 'burden' rather than an 'obstacle', though the problem of trying to have a 'master document' (usually in English) which will need to be tailored to local language, culture, and health economy as well as having to meet requirements of 'local' approval bodies.

This can mean that consents obtained may be dependent on the context (language, version of documents, etc.) in which the consent was obtained. It could mean that access to data (on the basis of consent) might not be universal. This would indeed be an 'obstacle', though not one yet encountered within IDERHA in reality.

Technology

#T1: Overhead in transposing data into diverse data exchange standards

One aspect is the range of 'data standards' in healthcare IT, so that different systems have adopted different standards based on locality, predominant systems, and historical accident. Once a 'standard' has been adopted with the systems of a particular data provider, then it becomes increasingly difficult to switch to a different standard.

This means that data holdings are in diverse formats (as well as being subject to subtle differences in the context of data collection, e.g. type of heart monitor, imaging device, etc.) and hence need to be shared in a more uniform fashion. The choice of OMOP provide a data exchange standard (given the heterogeneity of clinical information systems), but means that individual 'translators' need to be developed at each site and automated translation by e.g. AI driven engines have not yet been widely adopted effectively. This adds to the cost and complexity of setting up a 'node', as well as introducing further variations in data quality.

#T2: Unclear authentication needs

While IDERHA has chosen to follow EHDS in using eIDAS for digital identity authentication, the implementation of eIDAS-2 is still in progress; the Implementing Act for the EUDI Wallet was only agreed in November 2024.

While implementation is still in progress, actual adoption by organisations may well be a long way off, so IDERHA will struggle to find or lag implementation with data provider partners which support eIDAS for their clinical staff (so that citizens can chose to send their data to them from the citizen-app). While the citizen-app may help citizens to sign up for an eIDAS identity, this may prove a disincentive for potential users – and further may not be accepted by data providers as proof of ID (at least in the short-term) when submitting requests for a copy of their EHR data.

Data Analysis/Scientific

#D1: Real-world data are diverse

Scarcely a surprise (see #T1 above) and is part of the difficulty of getting RWE accepted as part of HTA. There is too much scope for selection bias (deliberate or otherwise) which may undermine its validity for answering scientific hypotheses. RWD should be far better at showing what works in practice or not – and some of the potential 'selection bias' may reflect patient and/or clinical choices, which should not be ignored.

This can also mean that different analytic tools may be needed to cope with the variability of data scope and quality. Equally, this may need to be born in mind when deploying AI techniques, where the variations by data collection context needs to be fully reflected in any conclusions drawn from model results. This is as much about avoiding perpetuating existing biases in healthcare delivery as properly interpreting cause and effect.

#D2: Data Quality standards

Data originally collected for direct clinical care delivery may not be of a sufficient 'quality' in comparison with data collected as part of an RCT, but the lack of quality may be compensated by quantity which allows for greater 'power' in any results/conclusions drawn.

Assessing the data quality of the recorded data (at least in terms of completeness, missingness, consistency, etc.) is still an art as there are no accepted 'standards' for gauging data quality for research purposes. Again, this is part of the IDERHA brief in terms of acceptability for HTA purposes rather than a specific data-sharing 'obstacle'